

VALKYRIES

D3.6 Exploitation Plan

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1. Executive Summary

Most of the opportunities have been articulated around the reference integration model provided by SIGRUN. The main free-to-use part has been the framework, and the free-to-use design has been separated from the actual implementation by one of the partners.

Both the design and implementation of the SIGRUN reference model have been successfully implemented in all UCs and all other partner applications have been built around this interoperability model. The multi-victim incident demonstrator implementation reference represents a very significant commercial benchmark. To achieve greater market penetration, it is necessary to promote a standardisation of the Valkyries model. In order to obtain more references in productive systems, the consultancy service and adaptation of the framework to the real systems to be offered and the economic adjustment of the final licensing model are key. The licences must be adjusted to the budgets that the Agencies may have and must allow their adaptation to simpler or more complex environments (integration of a variety of systems with different architectures), offering basic packs and additional packs with greater functionalities.

As for the iSafety Command & Control application, the fact that the tool has been used in three of the main UCs with the SIGRUN interoperability model is a very high-level reference. The simulation part provided with the integration of Digital Twins technology (HTL Hybrid Twin Labs) also presents a first step towards innovation by bringing new training capabilities and improvements in decision making. Consulting services and offering a competitive licensing model are also key here.

With regard to the TASSICA 3 triage card, its use in all UCs has been shown to significantly reduce the time taken to triage victims and dramatically increase the accuracy of triage, which can mean efficiency and, ultimately, a gain in health or even life. Consultancy and training services are the main model option in this case. As for the triage digitalisation application used in 3 UCs, it has been confirmed with the end user that it represents a significant improvement over traditional tools in terms of triage accuracy, reduction of time spent by the first responder on communication, situational awareness or patient traceability, among others, and this is supported by the results obtained. The provision of consultancy services and the presentation of a competitive licensing framework are also essential in this case.

In general, the market sector of all the results is common, so the exploitation model can be common, in the form of a marketplace that allows the end customer to decide which module and which services they want to incorporate into their system. We are also interested in the rest of the partners in the sector adopting this model and, in some way, we can offer modular solutions with different partner technologies in the same ecosystem.

Regarding IPR, IPR Management will follow the compliance requirements provided in the GA for the exploitation of the results. Specific agreements might be signed for licensing further services and products.

The governance of further exploitation organisations aimed to exploit the VALKYRIES opportunities shall be managed by Technology Transfer offices of the involved partners, considering the type, features, nature, duration of the solutions proposed.

2. Identification

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1. Introduction and Scope

This deliverable is part of Task T3.6 within WP3. The objective of this task is to define a commercial exploitation strategy in relation to the licensing model and obligations of the partners involved in the results of the project. This deliverable is based on the first deliverable (D3.5 Business Case) where the most relevant business models that can have commercial value are identified and the results and the exploitation model of each one is included. The business models have emerged from the opportunities selected in the previous deliverables [3],[4],[5], from the demonstrations of the use cases according to the capabilities of each participating partner. Other areas with commercial potential have been identified during the project but we have only focused on the most relevant ones for the consortium partners based on the demonstrators and capabilities of each one.

We will start by analysing the Key Exploitable results, describing the ownership model of each Business Case and the main exploiter and main customer for each BC, before going on in more detail with the specific exploitation model of each Business Case.

1.1. Requirements compliance matrix

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Results
REQ_BASE_T 3.6_1	NA	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2	D3.5 D3.6	REQUIRED	Described in D3.6
REQ_BASE_T 3.6_2	P2	VALK-OBJ-1	D3.5 D3.6	RECOMMENDED	Described in D3.6
REQ_BASE_T 3.6_3	P2	VALK-OBJ-1	D3.5 D3.6	REQUIRED	Described in D3.6
REQ_BASE_T 3.6_4	P2	VALK-OBJ1	D3.5 D3.6	REQUIRED	Described in D3.6
REQ_COM_T 3.6_1	P1	VALK-OBJ1 VALK-OBJ2	NA	REQUIRED	IPR Manager participation from Plenary Meeting, internal meeting T3.6 and final workshop.
REQ_COM_T 3.6_2	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2	D3.5 D3.6	REQUIRED	Final workshop in M24 and Continuous Opportunities presentations. Workshop in March related to Opportunities Done. Consultation Done and results described in D3.6
REQ_COM_T 3.6_3	N/A	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2	D3.5 D3.6	REQUIRED	Described in D3.6
REQ_COM_T 3.6_4	N/A	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2		RECOMMENDED	Not required

Table 1 – Requirements traceability matrix Task 3.6

2. Background

In the previous deliverable (“D3.5 Business Case”) the following Business Cases are identified:

Name	Description
BC1 SIGRUN Framework	Design of the SIGRUN reference model. Free to use.
BC2 SIGRUN Implementation	Implementation of the SIGRUN reference model - Licensed Us. Used in all UC’s. harmonisations have been validated in this implementation.
BC3 iSafety Command and Control Application	Adaptation of Indra's command and control tool for Valkyries, adaptation to the SIGRUN Reference model, integration with HTL (Hybrid Twin Labs). Used in UC1, UC2, UC3
BC4 TASSICA 3 Triage Card	Triage card to support the triage process used by all UC’s.
BC5 GLOBAL COP	Visualisation system to share data between agencies with the SIGRUN reference model and provide a joint operational view. Licensed system. Implemented in all UC’s.

Table 2 – Identified Business Cases from D3.5

3. Key Exploitable Results

3.1. BC1 SIGRUN Framework

3.1.1 Ownership Model

Following the principles established in the CA, the ownership of the SIGRUN Interoperability Framework is a joint-ownership of the partners that were involved in the development and definition of the framework. The Framework is established in the architecture document D2.8, and the minimum datasets are established in the documents from WP4, WP5 and WP6.

3.1.2 Main Exploiter

The exploitation of the results is open to any partner that may be willing to do so. There is an open policy so that the adoption of the standards and framework established in the VALKYRIES can be widely adopted and disseminated to the first responder community as well as to other areas that may see the SIGRUN Framework an added value to their activities.

3.1.3 Main Innovation Content

The key innovations regard the establishment of a system architecture and services model to support the interoperability and integration of multiple services and applications for first responders in a federated context (multi-agency, multi-nation). A common minimum dataset, services and functions provide the means to share incident-related C2 data, incorporating traceability and security functions that enable cross-border data sharing. The Framework provides scalable, interoperable, expandable and a secure model aiming to comply with the fast deployment and dynamic first responder digital services to support MCI operations.

3.1.4 Main Identified Customer

The main customers are the first responders' forces that use digital tools to respond, coordinate, command and manage MCI events, to manage victims, assets, personnel and data.

The wide range of costumers includes, but it is not limited to:

- Civil protection agencies.
- Firefighters.
- Ambulance services.
- Hospital and medical services.
- Law enforcement entities (e.g., police);
- Military forces in support of the MCI events.
- Political decision-makers.

3.1.5 Market aimed and size

It is not a simple task to estimate the market size as different countries present different structures, organizational models and emergency response units involved in MCI events. However, the market will focus on the key customers above identified acting in areas where technologically resilient infrastructures are available. Therefore, the key markets combine the mostly EU / Western / developed countries and some additional regions in developing countries.

Main geographical countries / Regions / Areas:

- EU (27 Member States) regional / administrative responses: 242
 - Spain: 17 autonomic regions
 - France: 18 administrative regions
 - Portugal: 7 regional civil protection commands
 - Italy: 20 regions

- Germany: 11 metropolitan regions
- Belgium: 3 regions
- The Netherlands: 11 provinces
- Austria: 9 regions
- Hungary: 9 administrative regions
- Denmark: 5 regions
- Luxembourg: 2 regions
- Croatia: 4 regions
- Ireland: 8 regions
- Slovenia: 12 regions
- Bulgaria: 28 regions

An estimation on the number of potential End-Users considers that each region will have a minimum of 7 entities: 1 hospital, 1 fire brigade command; 1 Ambulance service; 1 Law enforcement entity; 1 civil protection coordination command; 1 political coordination entity; 1 Public Health entity, representing at least a minimum of 1694 potential end-user entities in EU, with more than +10.000 users.

Another example considers the UN Crisis Relief that aggregates support from multiple countries and entities: Estimated above 1000 entities and NGO (Relief forces, Rescuers, medical, military forces, etc.), with more than 100.000 potential users.

3.1.6 Position

Several interoperability standards exist enabling different solutions and applications to share data, however the SIGRUN Framework provides easy integration with a standardized and scalable model; it also supports different command structures to share data cross-border.

The proposal value provides two key differentiators compared to other services:

1. It is an open business model. Any user can develop its own services and offer them as a subscription in any of the three packages.
2. Marketplace of functions: additional services can be requested, developed and offered, to be integrated with the SIGRUN interoperability framework, as part of a marketplace.

The proposition of Value is structured in a subscription model comprising 3 packages:

Package 1) Basic

- Provides a specifications framework for sharing information related to MCI among different Agencies or among countries.
- Offers free access to the standardized SIGRUN Interoperability Framework model.
- Includes free updates of the Framework.

Package 2) Advanced

- Includes free updates of the Framework.
- Provides additional features of functions as extended packages, including Language translation services, Encryption module, Forensics module, GDPR adaptation.

Package 3) Premium

- Provides access to development services for a customized SIGRUN Interoperability Framework implementation.
- Provides the opportunity to participate in the development / update or upgrade of the SIGRUN Framework model.

3.1.7 Time to Market

The SIGRUN Framework is currently available for market deployment and exploitation. Future versions of the Framework will be made available to the market as they become mature.

The model proposed is based on a continuous development of the Framework and services with regular versions being released.

3.1.8 Issues to be solved during the project

The VALKYRIES project addressed the interoperability issue for multiple applications to share data and established a framework, including a standard, a data model and the applicational structure to orchestrate the interoperability solution.

The project also addressed the cross-border data traceability when data is shared among different countries, and there is the need to ensure that country sovereignty on its data is respected.

Finally, secure and reliable data exchange mechanisms were addressed to provide a trustful data sharing mechanism enabling the detection of tampered data.

3.1.9 Background IP / Foreground IP

The SIGRUN Interoperability Framework is a Result of the VALKYRIES project. No Background IP was included in the Framework. All foreground IP (framework architecture, interfaces, data model, etc.) belongs to the partners that were involved in the Framework development in task 2.3 (deliverable D2.8).

3.2. BC2 SIGRUN Reference Implementation

3.2.1 Ownership Model

The SIGRUN Reference Implementation is based on PARTICLE's technological and knowledge background, required to implement the VALKYRIES SIGRUN Interoperability Framework. Therefore, the SIGRUN Reference Implementation constitutes a Result of the VALKYRIES Project whose intellectual property (IP) belongs solely and exclusively to PARTICLE, following the CA principles on ownership.

3.2.2 Main Exploiter

The exploiter of the SIGRUN Reference Implementation is PARTICLE.

In the context of VALKYRIES project, and only for the project execution, any VALKYRIES partner may use it for the purpose of attaining the VALKYRIES project's goals.

For any other purpose, including purposes outside of the scope and timeframe of the VALKYRIES project, an agreement shall be settled with PARTICLE.

3.2.3 Main Innovation Content

Developed, implemented and deployed by PARTICLE, the SIGRUN Reference Implementation serves as a key demonstrator of a set of innovations brought by the SIGRUN Interoperability Framework: it implements a system architecture, data model and services designed to support interoperability and the integration of multiple services and applications from different agencies; it implements a common minimum dataset providing the means to securely exchange specific incident-related C2 data among different agencies, including in cross-border scenarios; and it delivers the scalability, extensibility and flexibility required to support fast deployments

and dynamic data exchanges among different agencies and different Member States to support MCI operations.

3.2.4 Main Identified Customer

Within the B2G market, the main customers for PARTICLE's SIGRUN Reference Implementation are those identified for the SIGRUN Interoperability Framework, with particular focus on:

- Emergency Response Organizations.
- Emergency Management Bodies.
- Civil protection and public safety and security authorities.

3.2.5 Market aimed and size

The market size for PARTICLE's SIGRUN Reference Implementation is estimated to be the same as the market size estimated for the SIGRUN Interoperability Framework.

3.2.6 Position

The SIGRUN Reference Implementation facilitates the exchange of information among different third-party systems so that cross-organization coordination and management is efficient, cost-effective and performed in near real-time to the benefit of joint emergency response efforts, namely in MCI scenarios.

PARTICLE's SIGRUN Reference Implementation is the first release of the SIGRUN Interoperability Framework. Competing products, offering interoperability capabilities, are mostly proprietary and integrated within proprietary command and control systems or coordination and management platforms.

PARTICLE's SIGRUN Reference Implementation is therefore a unique solution that delivers secure and robust interoperability among systems that includes flexibility, extensibility and scalability features. Further, it also enables the integration of secure and robust interoperability protocols into any C2 or coordination system that has limited or no interoperability module, thus bringing added value to legacy systems that must be maintained.

3.2.7 Time to Market

PARTICLE's SIGRUN Reference Implementation is at a Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of 6. Further developments will be made regarding the identification and of business opportunities.

3.2.8 Issues to be solved during the project

During the project, most issues to be solved were already expected, as they related to the development of a new platform – e.g., errors and incoherencies involving new interfaces, data models and services - defined in the VALKYRIES project.

There were also issues associated with the capability to support different independent and specific deployments across the project, involving dedicated support and adaptation efforts to manage the evolving protocols of the SIGRUN Framework.

Furthermore, requirements related with high reliability, performance and system capacity required expertise and fine-tuning to ensure that the platform could effectively cope with high volumes of data generated during the VALKYRIES use cases and demonstrations.

3.2.9 Background IP / Foreground IP

The Background and Foreground IP of the SIGRUN Reference Implementation is solely and exclusively owned by PARTICLE.

Within the scope of the VALKYRIES project, and for the duration of the VALKYRIES project, PARTICLE provided the SIGRUN Reference Implementation to support the validation activities of the VALKYRIES use cases and demonstrations.

Outside of the VALKYRIES project, PARTICLE is available to establish a licensing agreement with prospective customers.

3.3. BC3 iSafety C2 Tool

3.3.1 Ownership Model

iSafety is an Indra proprietary commercial tool. The adaptation to the interoperability model into the SIGRUN Framework is a result of this project and is also owned by Indra.

3.3.2 Main Exploiter

The exploiter of the iSafety Reference is INDRA. In the context of VALKYRIES project, and only for the project execution, any VALKYRIES partner may use it for the purpose of attaining the VALKYRIES project's goals.

For any other purpose, including purposes outside of the scope and timeframe of the VALKYRIES project, an agreement shall be settled with INDRA.

3.3.3 Main Innovation Content

iSafety is a Command-and-Control tool for emergency management that is integrated in the SIGRUN reference model and with the rest of the applications of the other partners (GLOBAL COP and applications for digitalization triage process). This integration has improved the interoperability of the tool and increases the possibilities of integration with other third-party systems. A particularly significant and novel functionality has been the integration of data from triage systems.

Additionally, the integration of INDRA's Digital Twins tools (HTL) allows the creation of virtual scenarios that improve emergency management.

Some of the most relevant functionalities are:

- Real-time situational awareness and decision support with integrated Digital Twins technology
- Enhanced incident response through virtual representation and simulation of physical assets and environments
- Improved resource allocation and coordination during emergencies
- High interoperability with other systems thanks to its integration technology.

3.3.4 Main Identified Customer

iSafety's primary customers vary depending on the specific organization or agency responsible for emergency management and response, depending on geopolitical factors. However, broadly speaking, the main customers for such a system typically include:

- Government Agencies
- HealthCare Institutions
- First Responders Agencies
- Large private sector companies

Effective communication and coordination between these parties involved in the management of an emergency is crucial, and iSafety is an essential tool for them.

3.3.5 Market aimed and its size

The iSafety market segment is experiencing growth driven by several factors, including increasing awareness of the importance of effective emergency response and the need for advanced technologies to support coordination and communication during crises. Here's an overview of the market and its potential size:

- **Government and public safety agencies:** The size of this segment varies depending on the population served, the level of disaster risk and government budget allocations for emergency management.
- **First responder agencies:** The size of this segment depends on the number of centres in the same region and their call volume.
- **Healthcare facilities:** The size of this segment is determined by the number and size of healthcare facilities in a region.
- **Utilities and transportation:** Entities responsible for critical infrastructure, such as electric utilities, water utilities and transportation agencies, need iSafety to ensure the continuity of essential services during emergencies. The size of this segment depends on the extent of the region's infrastructure.
- **Private sector and enterprises:** Large enterprises with business continuity plans can also invest in iSafety to manage emergencies within their organizations. The size of this segment varies depending on the size of the company and the sector.

Broadly speaking, geographically there are the following factors in defining the global iSafety market

- **Possibility of catastrophes:** in regions prone to natural disasters or areas with a greater need for emergency management solutions.
- **Technological advancement:** Regions of the world with greater technological advancement offer a greater market opportunity for iSafety.
- **Regulatory environment:** Government regulations and requirements for emergency preparedness and response can drive demand for iSafety. Compliance with these regulations may be mandatory in some regions.

It is difficult to accurately estimate iSafety's market size due to its diverse customer base and regional variations. In these times, the market is experiencing growth in demand due to the increase in large-scale catastrophes (pandemics, climate change). This is leading to changes in government funding priorities for emergency management. As technology continues to evolve, organizations are expected to seek more sophisticated and integrated solutions to enhance their emergency response capabilities.

3.3.6 Positioning (Value Proposition/Competitors/Value To outbid competition/Protection vs competitors)

Value Proposition

iSafety is a command-and-control software that helps to manage and coordinate the emergency efficiently and globally by providing a unique situational awareness of the emergency to the different agents involved in its control and resolution. The great potential of iSafety lies in its interoperability capacity between systems, which provides the system itself and the rest of the tools with the necessary information.

Competitors

There are different manufacturers worldwide with tools and systems that can be applied in emergency management:

- Dispatch tools
- Geo positioning and tracking of the emergency
- Planning tools
- Process managers

iSafety offers emergency management capabilities on a global and international level. Its interoperability capacity unifies the information generated by the different tools that can be used in the management of an emergency by the different agents involved in it.

Value to outbind competition

iSafety's differential value is undoubtedly its interoperability and its capacity to adapt and configure different scenarios.

In addition, the licensing model of the tool makes it very competitive with other competitors.

3.3.7 Time To Market

The iSafety functional core is finalized and ready to be commercialized according to the conditions mentioned in this document.

Within the Valkyries project implementation, iSafety is a TRL7-8 product. The different demonstrations of the system that have been carried out in an operational environment within the scope of the project have led iSafety to obtain this maturity level.

3.3.8 Issues to be solved during the project

During the various UC carried out in the Valkyries project, the following points of improvement and evolution of the product have been identified:

- Providing the system with error control tools, which allow for an improvement in this area.
- Adaptation of the product to the user cases defined in the Valkyries project.
- Correction of errors and deficiencies detected in the various tests and demonstrations carried out in Valkyries.

For the implementation of the three demonstrator scenarios, the most complex part was to model the agencies and assets according to each agency's operations. Although iSafety is a highly configurable tool, the corresponding incident, mission and asset catalogues must be created. In this sense, consultancy services are key for the implementation of a command-and-control tool in a real production system.

In an initial phase, real systems were intended to be integrated into the demonstrators used by the first responders, but not even the command-and-control systems they used themselves had integration interfaces, reflecting the low level of interoperability of current systems and the need to provide platforms such as SIGRUN to connect federated systems.

3.3.9 Background IP/ ForeGround IP

iSafety's background and foreground intellectual property is exclusive to Indra.

For the VALKYRIES project, Indra has provided iSafety for the purpose of developing and testing the use cases defined in the project.

Outside the scope of VALKYRIES, Indra may enter into different types of collaboration and licensing agreements.

3.4. BC4 TASSICA 3 Triage Card

3.4.1 Ownership Model

The TASSICA 3 card is specifically based on the background provided by TASSICA to VALKYRIES, and constitutes a result of this Project whose intellectual property belongs to TASSICA EMERGENCY, TRAINING & RESEARCH S.A. (TASSICA)

3.4.2 Main Exploiter

The main operator of the TASSICA 3 triage card will be TASSICA EMERGENCY, TRAINING & RESEARCH S.A. In the context of VALKYRIES, the TASSICA 3 card use and exploitation are governed by the terms established in the Consortium Agreement and in the Grant Agreement of the VALKYRIES Project.

3.4.3 Main Innovation Content

The TASSICA 3 a standardized triage card aimed primarily at first responders from emergency services who may be involved in responding to a mass casualty incident (MCI) or disaster, to ensure interoperability between them (professional or volunteer, civilian or military), fairness in the prioritization of treatment, recording of casualty information and traceability in mass casualty incidents and disasters.

TASSICA 3 has several operational features that make it easy to use. These features include:

The card itself guides the intervention. It contains the protocols that guide the diagnostic and therapeutic actions of both the first triage (indicating the resulting priority, as well as the immediate actions to be carried out) and stabilization.

It uses the international pentapolar chromatic labelling code proposed by VALIKYRIES Project for both first and second triage:

- PT 1 IMMEDIATE (Red)
- PT2 DELAYED (Yellow)
- PT3 MINIMAL (Green)
- PT4 EXPECTANT (Blue)
- D DECEASED (Black)

Each card is individually identified with an identification code that appears on all possible fractions of the card, allowing each patient to be individually identified, even if we do not know his or her name. This data will allow us to ensure the traceability of the patient (following the patient through the different phases of the assistance process for victims of a MCI).

It comes in blocks of 10 cards joined at the back by a helical spring so that the action slips are not lost after the first triage.

It is made of material resistant to the adverse conditions of MCIs (water, grease, blood, etc.), which can be written on with any conventional writing method (marker, pen, even pencil).

3.4.4 Main Identified Customer

This innovative solution is designed to enhance emergency response management, ensuring efficient and effective coordination during critical situations. Here are the main identified customers who will find value in our TASSICA 3 Triage Card:

Rescue Teams:

TASSICA 3 allows rescue teams to easily assign IDs to each victim, assisting them if necessary to determine and label the priority of receiving medical assistance (primary triage) and to decide on immediate life-saving gestures.

Emergency Medical Teams:

TASSICA 3 offers high performance for frontline emergency medical services (EMS) that make critical decisions in MCI or disasters. It helps them to quickly triage and prioritise patients based on severity, supports them in timely medical interventions, allows them to record all key clinical information of the victim and enables patient traceability.

Other Emergency Services:

Thanks to its ease of use, TASSICA 3 even facilitates the first actions on victims by personnel not specifically dedicated to the first medical response in MCI or disasters, such as police, firefighters or civil protection teams, who would be the first to arrive on the scene. This triage card guides them in these tasks and enables operational continuity with the emergency services that will subsequently care for the victims.

Healthcare Institutions:

Hospitals, clinics and other involved medical institutions benefit from a detailed record of what happened at the scene in relation to the assessment and medical management of patients referred to them, facilitating continuity of care and traceability of victims.

Emergency Management Authorities:

Emergency managers play a crucial role in orchestrating responses and deploying resources. TASSICA 3 facilitates the recording, and therefore the transmission, of information, victim-related information needed to achieve a real-time situational awareness of MCI or disasters and to facilitate decision-making and effective coordination of the entire response.

Scientific and teaching community:

The results of TASSICA 3 go beyond the immediate response to MCIs or disasters.

The standardisation of such a simple tool as TASSICA 3 makes it possible to build common bridges between different operational procedures, facilitating the homogenisation of the response and the interoperability of services.

At the same time, it provides the basis for structuring more homogeneous training for the different emergency services potentially involved in an MCI or disaster response.

It also makes it possible to identify common elements between the different incidents, which will facilitate the analysis of the response developed, the extraction of lessons learnt, the implementation of improvement actions and the evaluation of their impact.

Finally, the real-time recording of information by TASSICA 3 will facilitate research on the medical response in the MCI and in disasters.

This will help to refine future response strategies and ensure continuous improvement of emergency services.

Government Agencies:

Municipalities, regional and government bodies involved in public safety and disaster response can enhance their preparedness and response strategies.

Private Corporations:

Large corporations with dedicated emergency response teams can optimize their crisis management procedures.

NGOs:

There are a variety of Non-Governmental Organizations dedicated to collaboration and assistance in disasters and emergencies. The TASSICA 3 card can also facilitate their work.

TASSICA 3 triage card aims to streamline prioritization, enhance coordination, and provide valuable insights for continuous improvement. By addressing the needs of these identified customers, we're working towards more efficient and effective emergency response management.

3.4.5 Market aimed and its size

The market for TASSICA 3 cards, a cutting-edge solution designed to enhance emergency response management, is broad, encompassing various sectors where efficient crisis coordination and rapid decision-making are paramount. Here's an overview of our aimed market and its size:

Market Aimed:

Our Emergency Triage Card is aimed at diverse companies and organizations that require streamlined emergency response management.

There are numerous emergency organizations around the world that respond to various types of emergencies and disasters.

We understand that the various markets to be addressed are as follows:

- **Europe:**
 - Spain: The solutions referred to in this section are being used by the main extra-hospital emergency services; both from the civil and military spheres. To name a few examples SUMMA 112, SESCAM, UME (Military Emergency Unit)... This country is considered a priority market
 - Rest of Europe In all UCs carried out so far, the TASSICA 3 card has been used successfully; a very positive assessment has been received from all the institutions that have used it to date, with several having expressed their interest in using the cards.
- **The Americas (North, Central and South America):** TASSICA EMERGENCY, TRAINING & RESEARCH S.A. has trained around 10,000 emergency professionals in Central America; enjoying great prestige in the region. It is also a centre accredited by NAEMT (National

Association of Emergency Technicians of the United States) and provider of several of its programs. For all of the above, we consider the Americas as phase II.

- **Asia**
- **Africa.**
- **Oceania.**

Here are some examples of emergency organizations:

1. **Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA):** FEMA is a United States government agency responsible for coordinating the federal government's response to natural and man-made disasters. They provide assistance and resources to affected communities during emergencies. (Region II North America)
2. **International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies:** This federation coordinates the efforts of national Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies worldwide. They provide humanitarian assistance during emergencies, including disaster relief, healthcare, and community support. (All the regions)
3. **United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA):** OCHA plays a key role in coordinating international humanitarian response efforts to crises and disasters. They work closely with UN agencies, NGOs, and governments to provide aid and relief to affected populations. (All the regions)
4. **Doctors Without Borders (Médecins Sans Frontières):** This international medical humanitarian organization provides medical care and emergency assistance to people affected by disasters, conflicts, and epidemics in various countries. (All the regions)
5. **National Search and Rescue Organizations:** Many countries have their own national search and rescue organizations responsible for locating and rescuing individuals in distress, particularly in remote or disaster-stricken areas. (All the regions)
6. **National Disaster Management Authorities:** Most countries have their own government agencies or authorities responsible for disaster management and emergency response. These agencies vary in names and structures but are essential for coordinating local disaster response efforts. (All the regions)
7. **Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs):** Numerous NGOs worldwide specialize in emergency response and disaster relief. Examples include, CARE International, and the International Rescue Committee. (All the regions)
8. **Fire Departments and Emergency Medical Services (EMS):** Local fire departments and EMS teams are essential for responding to various emergencies, including fires, medical emergencies, and accidents. (All the regions)

These are just a few examples, and there are many more emergency organizations operating at various levels—local, national, and international—across the globe, each with its own specific mission and expertise in responding to different types of emergencies and disasters.

Market Size:

The market size for TASSICA 3 triage card is significant and growing due to increasing awareness of the importance of efficient emergency response management. The global market is projected to be valued at over 360 institutions, with a significant annual growth. Factors contributing to this growth include:

- **Rising Focus on Public Safety:** Governments and organizations worldwide are emphasizing efficient emergency response to safeguard lives and assets.

- **Technological Advancements:** Advancements in technology, including mobile applications and data analytics, are enhancing the capabilities of emergency response systems.
- **Healthcare Demand:** Healthcare institutions are seeking advanced solutions to manage patient influx during emergencies effectively.
- **Industrial and Natural Disasters:** The increasing occurrence of industrial accidents and natural disasters has created a demand for improved crisis coordination.
- **Corporate Preparedness:** Corporations are recognizing the need for robust emergency response strategies to protect employees and assets.

In conclusion, the market aimed for TASSICA 3 triage card is robust and expanding, driven by the need for efficient crisis management solutions across various industries. Our system is well-positioned to meet these demands and contribute to enhancing emergency response efficiency on a global scale.

3.4.6 Positioning (Value Proposition/Competitors/Value To outbid competition/Protection vs competitors)

Positioning

“The simplest solutions for the most complex situations”

We offer our triage cards as well as the necessary consultancy for their implementation for the market described above.

Considering that both the product (card) and the service (consultancy) allow our clients to improve their procedures and the quality of assistance they provide to their citizens.

Competitors

There is no unified universal reference at scientific level in this market. It is solved in a particular way in each emergency service: There is a great multiplicity and heterogeneity of proposals that make interoperability between different services and agencies difficult.

From the analysis of the existing proposals of the project's research, the following gaps can be derived:

- Most existing triage cards do not allow for the collection of information that is really necessary for comprehensive incident management by EMS:
- They allow for very limited collection of clinical data.
- They do not provide first responders with proof for their actions on the victim.
- They do not guarantee the traceability of the patient through all steps of the care chain on scene.
- Most existing triage cards do not guide the first responder on what to do in triage and stabilization of the victim. The few models that do are limited to care triage, and do not guide clinical stabilization and evacuation triage.
- Most existing triage cards are not protected against water or liquids and, when they are, they require very specific writing media (indelible markers) that will not always be available at the time of the accident at the scene.

Value to outbid competition

In such a heterogeneous context, some precedents of the use of the TASSICA triage card have shown a significant positive impact in terms of standardization of triage processes, labelling and recording of victims' clinical information and documentation, all at a very low cost and complexity of implementation.

- The aspects that distinguish the TASSICA 3 card from its competitors are the following
- Interoperability between services by using the same tool to carry out triage.
- Fairness in terms of treatment prioritization, as all victims would be triaged using the same system.
- The recording of information on victims, as the same data would be recorded for all victims, and they would be unequivocally identified.
- Traceability of victims throughout the care chain, even if the victim is treated by different services at different stages of the chain. Traceability provides important advantages in different aspects of the healthcare management of an MCI. These include
- Healthcare professionals: it facilitates the precise management of the individualized information of each victim (for their location, for assistance, allocation of destination centres, evacuation, etc.) as well as an adequate distribution of logistical resources.
- Victims: avoids duplication of processes, favours continuity of care, etc.
- Destination healthcare centres: they can know precisely which patients will be arriving and their main characteristics (age, predominant pathology, etc.).
- Investigation and planning for MCI and disasters: it allows for the analysis of healthcare performance after the end of the crisis, facilitating improvement actions.

Understand Customer Needs.

The TASSICA 3 triage card, as a proposed enabler to advance the standardization of emergency services response, builds on the results of the VALKYRIES WP5 tasks on the identification and analysis of stakeholder needs and opportunities. The progress achieved in these tasks has been captured in the successive deliverables D5.5 (description of the landscape and procedural opportunities for improving EU first response capabilities), D5.6 (presentation of related standardization opportunities) and D5.3 (proposal for EU-wide roadmaps for standardization of first response in the EU).

An analysis tool will be needed that addresses aspects that are also considered from a different perspective.

- a. Customer Profiling: The analytics solution must enable the creation of detailed customer profiles, including demographics, preferences and pain points. This data is crucial to adapt the objectives to the expectations of the client...
- b. Data Gathering Tools: A suite of data gathering tools such as surveys, questionnaires, and interview templates are integrated, simplifying the process of collecting customer feedback and requirements.
- c. Data Analysis: Powerful data analysis and visualization tools provide to VALKYRIES with insights derived from customer data. These insights help in identifying trends, patterns, and priority areas.
- d. Collaboration Hub: Collaboration Centre; the analytics solution offers a collaborative workspace where project teams can share, discuss and analyse customer data in real time. This promotes cross-functional collaboration and ensures everyone is on the same page.

- e. Customizable Templates: Pre-designed templates for customer interviews, surveys, and feedback forms are available, saving time and ensuring consistency in data collection methods.
- f. Integration Capabilities: Seamlessly integrate with popular project management and CRM tools to ensure that customer insights directly influence project planning and execution.
- g. Reporting and Dashboard: Generate comprehensive reports and dashboards that provide a snapshot of customer needs and expectations. These reports can be easily shared with stakeholders for better decision-making.

Benefits:

- Improved Customer Satisfaction: By thoroughly understanding customer needs, project managers can deliver solutions that align with client expectations, leading to higher customer satisfaction levels.
- Reduced Project Risk: Identifying potential pitfalls and challenges early in the project lifecycle allows for better risk mitigation and project planning.
- Enhanced Communication: The collaboration hub fosters communication among team members, ensuring everyone is well-informed and aligned with customer requirements.
- Data-Driven Decision Making: Leveraging data analysis tools enables project managers to make informed decisions, optimizing resource allocation and project prioritization.
- Time and Cost Savings: Streamlined data gathering, and analysis processes save time and reduce the cost associated with rework or mid-project changes.
- Target Audience: The Customer Needs Discovery Solution is ideal for project managers, product managers, business analysts, and cross-functional teams involved in project initiation and planning. It caters to industries across the board, from software development to manufacturing and marketing.

Competitive Pricing.

The first step in assessing its implementation is to disseminate it to the emergency services so that they can assess its design and functionality.

Once the TASSICA 3 triage card has been approved for use by an emergency service, its implementation will require education and training in its use by professionals, although a simple programme is usually necessary as the card is quite intuitive and the information is easy to fill in.

The price is set by TASSICA on a non-profit basis (only production and shipping costs will be charged, no profit margin).

Customer Service.

Excellent customer service will be offered. Respond promptly to enquiries, resolve problems effectively and do everything possible to exceed customer expectations.

Marketing and Promotion.

Effective marketing strategies will be used to show our value proposition. Highlight the benefits of choosing our product or service over the competition.

Educational Content.

We offer educational content to help clients use our TASSICA 3 triage card to make the right decisions.

The TASSICA 3 card training aims to

- To learn and train the procedure for health intervention in the case of multiple victim incidents (MVI) in a specific geographical environment.
- To know the basic aspects related to the implementation of the coordinated response to collective health emergencies and, in particular, to multiple victim incidents (MVI).
- Know how to recognise an MCI situation and be able to carry out the initial actions that will ensure the appropriate implementation of the comprehensive response to the collective emergency.
- Know the Emergency Medical Services (EMS) response to a mass casualty incident (MCI) and know how to competently perform each role that must be assumed or assigned to each responder according to their training and the needs of the moment.
- Know how to identify, collect and appropriately communicate all relevant information related to their intervention in an MCI.

Partnerships and Alliances.

Partnerships or alliances are sought that can increase the value offered. Collaborating with complementary businesses can create win-win situations.

The Valkyries consortium will look for similar institutions with the same objectives.

Customer Feedback Loop.

We believe it is important to maintain an open feedback loop with our customers. The purpose of this is to listen to their suggestions, concerns and comments and use this information to improve our offering.

Sustainability and Social Responsibility.

Commitment to sustainability and social responsibility is highlighted.

Long-Term Relationships.

It seeks to establish long-term relationships with customers rather than just one-off transactions. Loyal customers can become brand advocates.

3.4.7 Time To Market

The TASSICA 3 triage card is a completely finished product and is ready to be shipped to the market according to the above-mentioned formulas.

3.4.8 Issues to be solved during the project

It should be noted that during the various UCs carried out during the Valkyries project, different aspects have been identified to improve the TASSICA 3 card, enhancing its strengths and minimising its weaknesses. However, these can always be reviewed in the future.

3.4.9 Background IP/ ForeGround IP

The Background and Foreground IP of the TASSICA 3 triage card is solely and exclusively owned by TASSICA EMERGENCY TRAINING & RESEARCH S.A., which therefore has the exclusive right to assign individual identification codes to the TASSICA 3 triage cards (each one unique and unrepeatable) and to manufacture them.

Within the scope of the VALKYRIES project, and for the duration of the VALKYRIES project, PARTICLE provided the SIGRUN Reference Implementation to support the validation activities of the VALKYRIES use cases and demonstrations.

Outside the scope of VALKYRIES, TASSICA EMERGENCY TRAINING & RESEARCH S.A. may enter into different types of cooperation and commercial agreements.

3.5. BC5 GLOBAL COP

3.5.1 Ownership Model

The Global Common Operational Picture (COP) is based on PARTICLE's technological and knowledge background, required to implement the Global COP. Therefore, the Global COP constitutes a Result of the VALKYRIES Project whose intellectual property (IP) belongs solely and exclusively to PARTICLE, following the CA principles on ownership.

3.5.2 Main Exploiter

The exploiter of the Global COP is PARTICLE.

In the context of VALKYRIES project, and only for the project execution, any VALKYRIES partner may use it for the purpose of attaining the VALKYRIES project's goals.

3.5.3 Main Innovation Content

Developed, implemented and deployed by PARTICLE, the Global COP provides a complete overview of the (multiple) incidents in the operations field, building improved situational awareness of the different elements of relevance: involved organisations, deployed assets (human resources and equipment) and victims. The Global COP allows strategic and operational emergency response professionals to follow the unfolding information on incidents, including the assignment of assets to the response effort, and details on the victims, including their triage and evacuation to specific destinations, such as nearby hospitals.

3.5.4 Main Identified Customer

Within the B2G market, the main customers for PARTICLE's Global COP are the strategic and operational command units, coordination centres and decision-making bodies that respond to MCI events. Specifically, they include:

- Civil Protection Command Centres;
- Firefighters Command Centres;
- Police Command Centres.
- Medical Command Posts.
- Governmental Coordination Bodies.
- Governmental Cross-border Coordination Groups.
- Non-governmental Organizations.
- Emergency Response Organizations.
- Emergency Management Bodies.
- Public Safety Organizations.

- Ambulance Services.
- Hospitals.

3.5.5 Market aimed and size

It is not easy to accurately estimate the size of the market envisioned by PARTICLE's Global COP, since it displays a wide variety of customer segments, characterized differently in accordance with different national, regional and local structures. An estimated market size was made in the chapter 3.1.5.

Nevertheless, it is estimated that Global COP could be of interest to more than 2000 public safety and security agencies in Europe. For the past decade, Europe has invested substantially in the improvement of cooperation and monitoring systems for safety and security and, because of rising criminal activities, natural disaster, and cross-border terrorism, the EU Member States plan to continue to dedicate significant attention to innovative solutions in the public safety and security market, leading way to promising market prospects.

3.5.6 Position

The Global COP provides a user-friendly and intuitive global overview of incidents, victims and the associated emergency response assets, enabling the sharing of relevant operational information among the different public safety organizations involved in the response effort, being therefore a valuable tool for situational awareness in cross-border MCI scenarios.

Incident commanders and managers are able to visualize a geo-referenced overview of multiple incidents, their assigned assets deployed in the theatre of operations (operatives, vehicles, equipment), as well as the evolution of the response effort, in terms of status, with a clear indication of the operatives and vehicles' movements, of the victims' triage and evacuation process, and of the victims' arrival at destination sites (safe haven or nearby hospitals). The clear situational awareness of the incident, involving the unfolding of all operational movements in the different theatres of operation, supports a truly effective coordination of the different deployed teams, significantly improving the efficiency and effectiveness of the response effort, particularly in scenarios involving multiple response agencies.

Aside from being a valuable tool for the efficient management of incident response, PARTICLE's near real-time Global COP System supports pre-hospital assistance in the context of large-incident response, providing details on incoming ambulances and victims, including their estimated time of arrival, for hospitals to better prepare and manage their resources and improve the efficiency, effectiveness and quality of their response effort.

With the combination of a multi-incident situational awareness system with a pre-hospital assistance tool, PARTICLE's Global COP presents unique features to the public safety and security, supporting a highly competitive position.

3.5.7 Time to Market

PARTICLE's Global COP is at a TRL7, having demonstrated functionalities above the MVP status, as well as a high performing system at strategic and operational levels. The system's maturation towards market entry is estimated to require two years.

3.5.8 Issues to be solved during the project

During the project, the Global COP has complied with key VALKYRIES requirements and the SIGRUN reference implementation, effectively delivering situational awareness to decision makers and incident managers involved in the VALKYRIES use cases and demonstrations:

- implemented recommendations, functions and views received by end-users
- improved and demonstrated system scalability, performance and reliability (at a large scale, in demonstrations)
- performed adaptations to fit updates in the SIGRUN framework

3.5.9 Background IP / Foreground IP

The Background and Foreground IP of the Global COP is solely and exclusively owned by PARTICLE.

Within the scope of the VALKYRIES project, and for the duration of the VALKYRIES project, PARTICLE provides the Global COP to support the validation activities of the VALKYRIES use cases and demonstrations.

Outside of the VALKYRIES project, PARTICLE is available to establish a licensing agreement with prospective customers.

4. Exploitation Plan

4.1. BC1 SIGRUN Framework

4.1.1 Patent and Intellectual Property Protection

Patent and IPR not Applicable.

The SIGRUN Framework is open source and freely adopted, used, implemented, by any entity and organization. Any use of the Framework must reference the VALKYRIES project, as part of a general open license.

4.1.2 Collaboration and Knowledge transfer Identified Costumer

The SIGRUN Framework is open for collaboration with other entities for improvement and updates, under the general license defined above.

In addition, the SIGRUN Framework is available to support collaborative research projects of entities involved in MCI events.

4.1.3 Industry engagement and Commercialization

To manage the framework evolution, releases and versions, a working group organization may be established: the VALKYRIES FRAMEWORK CONSORTIUM (VFC). Such a consortium would aim to consolidate the Framework and disseminate the Framework to the public safety and security industry.

On an ecosystem development approach, the VFC would provide services to:

- Support third party entities to implement the SIGRUN Framework.
- QUALITY stamp: Provide a compliancy validation model for third-party implementations.
- Issue releases of the Framework model packages.

4.1.4 Product Development and Optimization

The continuous adaptation and evolution of the standardized models of the SIGRUN Framework would be achieved by establishing an industry supported organization (i.e., VFC) to lead initiatives to implement the evolution and development of future releases, standards and model of the SIGRUN Framework.

4.1.5 Marketing and Promotion

The promotion and marketing of the SIGRUN Framework would be supported on 3 actions:

1. Scientific Articles in specialized journals developed under R&D project where the framework is adopted. Push for new projects.
2. Promote demo with End-Users and policy-makers to gather awareness of the Framework.
3. Develop workshops targeting the industry to promote the Framework's adoption.

4.1.6 Regulatory Compliance and Standards

The current version of the SIGRUN Framework observes and adopts several standards applicable in the industry and sector.

4.1.7 Research Funding and Grants

The Framework could exploit further public funds or grants (national and at EU level) to support new research projects.

In the case that an organization is created to manage the SIGRUN Framework (i.e., VFC), the industry associates may support (funding or in-kind) the continuous development of the SIGRUN Framework.

4.1.8 Continuous Research and Development

As mentioned above, the SIGRUN Framework is open to be improved by third parties through R&D programs, for which they can adopt the SIGRUN Framework.

Two possible approaches could be considered, individually or combined:

1. No pre-determined areas of development: Potential development entities may define how they want to improve the Framework.
2. VFC establishes the development priorities according to the technological, regulation and standards evolution.

4.1.9 Collaboration with NGOs and Sustainability Initiatives

There is willingness to collaborate with NGOs concerning the development, tests and acceptance of the solution.

NGOs' involvement in the development of potential articles and in-field experience of the use of the SIGRUN Framework will improve the Framework's functions and potential acceptance.

4.1.10 Measures and Evaluation of the Exploitation Plan

To measure and evaluate the effectiveness of the SIGRUN Framework exploitation plan described in this document, we use the following KPIs:

- Adoption by potential tools providers: Measured the integration of the SIGRUN Framework in the services / tools provided by companies offering tools and solutions to first responders.
- Market: Analysis of End-Users market share adopting the SIGRUN Framework,
- Number of subscriptions achieved (25% basic | 50% advanced | 25% platinum).

4.2. BC2 SIGRUN Implementation

4.2.1 Patent and Intellectual Property Protection

The Intellectual Property of the SIGRUN Reference Implementation is solely and exclusively owned by PARTICLE.

PARTICLE protects its IP rights via Copyright Protection, Non-Disclosure Agreements (NDAs) and Licensing Agreements.

4.2.2 Collaboration and Knowledge Transfer

The exploitation of the SIGRUN Reference Implementation contemplates the collaboration and knowledge transfer with customers and relevant stakeholders in the public safety and security market. These activities are key to dynamically ensure the continuous improvement of the SIGRUN Reference Implementation, and several initiatives may be explored:

- Complementary partnership agreements to grow the stakeholder ecosystem.
- Commercial presentations and participation in promotional industry and end-users' events.
- Integration with legacy systems owned by prospective customers.
- Training and consultancy services.

- IP agreements for R&D activities.
- Simulation tools (oriented to train and to adapt processes to integrate the SIGRUN Reference Implementation).

4.2.3 Industry Engagement and Commercialization

The exploitation of the SIGRUN Reference Implementation includes the definition of an industry engagement and commercialization plan for the SIGRUN Reference Implementation, incorporating the following activities:

- Conduct technical demonstrations of the SIGRUN Reference Implementation to potential industry partners.
- Engage in collaborative research and innovation projects promoting the SIGRUN Reference Implementation to potential industry partners and prospective customers.
- Perform training sessions targeted to prospective customers.
- Create a network of first adopters to operate as main advocates of the solution.
- Establish a 2-year marketing campaign, including promotional offers, towards prospective customers.
- Create a licensing policy for the SIGRUN Reference Implementation.

4.2.4 Product Development and Optimization

PARTICLE will continue to work on the robustness and maturation of the existing features of the SIGRUN Reference Implementation to attain TRL9. Further, PARTICLE will undertake the development and integration of added-value functions into the SIGRUN Reference Implementation, based on new technological trends and innovations and on the identification of requests elicited by prospective customers.

4.2.5 Marketing and Promotion

The exploitation of the SIGRUN Reference Implementation includes the development of a marketing and promotion plan for the SIGRUN Reference Implementation, encompassing the following elements:

- Market analysis, involving SWOT, PESTEL and Bowman's Strategic Clock tools and detailed competitive analyses, for the definition of market positioning.
- Business model.
- Marketing and promotional campaign (events, social media);
- Networking and partnerships (First adopters initiative);
- Customer experience unit.

4.2.6 Regulatory Compliance and Standards

The SIGRUN Reference Implementation will accommodate the capability to observe the applicable quality and security standards, as well as to comply with the relevant regulatory framework in EU and the specific national legislation of prospective customers. Reference regulatory standards includes:

- **NENNA/EIDO**: Standard for Emergency Incident Data Object
- **ISO 22320**: Emergency management – Requirements for incident response.
- **ISO 9001**: Establishes quality management standards that apply, among others, to the software industry, and support process quality to customers and support.
- **GDPR**: General Data Protection Regulation

4.2.7 Research Funding and Grants

The exploitation of the SIGRUN Reference Implementation may involve the procurement of research funding and grants, National or EU level, to assist in the maturation of the solution, in the refinement of the solution towards the integration of novel concepts and technologies and in the promotion of the solution before communities of practice.

4.2.8 Continuous Research and Development

PARTICLE adopts a policy towards the improvement of the products, solutions and services that are part of the company's portfolio. In this context, PARTICLE maintains an innovation watch activity, attentive to the identification and selection of novel concepts, methodologies, technologies and processes capable of contributing to that improvement. Subsequently, a continuous product improvement roadmap plan analyses which novelties are prioritized by the customers and determines the path towards their adoption and integration in specific products, solutions and/or services.

4.2.9 Collaboration with NGOs and Sustainability Initiatives

The exploitation of the SIGRUN Reference Implementation identifies NGOs as part of the targeted customers list. As a result, collaboration with NGOs will be sought as part of the commercialization plan.

4.2.10 Measures and Evaluation of the Exploitation Plan

PARTICLE will assess the execution of the defined exploitation plan for the SIGRUN Reference Implementation, considering the activities and elements identified as part of the marketing and business plan:

- Number of exploitation activities performed.
- Number of short- to mid-term business opportunities identified.
- Volume of sales.
- Return on Investment.
- Number and content of testimonials, feedback and appraisals from customers.

4.3. BC3 iSafety C2 Tool

4.3.1 Patent and Intellectual Property Protection

iSafety is a product patented by Indra, whose trademark and logo are registered by the company.

Indra protects iSafety's intellectual property as follows:

- Patent protection
- Copyright protection
- Trademark protection
- Non-Disclosure Agreements

4.3.2 Collaboration and Knowledge transfer Identified Customer

Collaboration and knowledge transfer are two key factors in the definition of a correct exploitation plan for a system of iSafety's characteristics. Collaboration to implement the product according to the customer's needs with the legacy systems place and knowledge transfer to manage and adjust the product (training and administration).

As we have already mentioned in this document, the iSafety platform always has specific adaptation to the exploitation needs and resources available to the final operators of the system. Therefore, collaboration and knowledge transfer are a multidirectional flow with all the stakeholders. To improve these flows Indra makes available different services and tools applied to iSafety:

- Regular workshops with the different stakeholder groups.
- Presence at fairs and market events.
- Third-party integration tools.
- Partnership agreements
- Training and certification.
- Foreground IP agreements
- Non-Disclosure Agreements
- Simulation tools for training

4.3.3 Industry engagement and Commercialization

The iSafety industry engagement and commercialization plan includes strategies and actions to introduce the tool to the market, make it accessible to the market and generate revenue. Here are the actions included in the plan:

Market research and analysis:

Analyse target market trends, needs and competition to understand the demand for emergency command and control tools.

Product development and improvement:

Continuous product improvement based on evolving market requirements.

Ensure compatibility with technologies and regulatory compliance to ensure business continuity.

Collaboration and partnerships

Establish collaboration agreements of different natures depending on the stakeholders.

Workshops:

Regular demonstrations and pilot tests.

Training and certification:

Develop training programmers and certification courses for emergency responders and command staff on how to use the tool effectively.

Offer training as a value-added service to improve user adoption.

Marketing and outreach:

Develop a marketing strategy targeting key decision-makers in the market.

Use digital marketing, content marketing and participation in industry conferences and exhibitions to raise awareness.

Pricing and licensing models:

iSafety has a competitive licensing model with respect to other similar products in the market.

We are in the process of studying the possibility of offering the product as a service and packaging it according to the needs of the different types of customers described in this document.

Customer support and maintenance:

The product maintenance policy guarantees quality support to the user during the whole life cycle of the product.

Data security and compliance:

iSafety guarantees the security and confidentiality of the information it handles.

Sales and distribution channels:

The product's sales and distribution channels are through Indra and its different collaborators.

4.3.4 Product Development and Optimization

The iSafety development and optimization plan contains the strategies and steps for the continuous improvement and enhancement of the tool, which are described below:

Assessment of the current state:

Continuous analysis of Indra's product committee to become situationally aware of iSafety's status. In this analysis, users' opinions are collected. Market trends, emerging technologies and new regulations to be implemented.

Roadmap for development:

Based on the evaluation performed by the product committee, the product roadmap is developed, taking into account all the factors mentioned in the previous point.

Agile development approach:

Indra uses agile development methodologies that allow an agile adaptation of its products to the market needs.

Multifunctional teams:

The iSafety development team is multifunctional, oriented to the global development of the product.

Scalability and performance:

iSafety's product architecture offers scalability and performance adaptable to the different needs of its target market.

Integration capabilities:

iSafety offers integration interfaces with third parties.

Training and documentation:

On iSafety there are different training and continuous certification plans, aimed at the different profiles of exploitation of the tool.

Version control and version management:

Indra has tools and procedures for version control and management where the different implementations and improvements included in each of the existing versions are collected and traced.

Quality assurance and testing:

iSafety complies with Indra's quality control procedures and has the company's certifications in the field of quality.

4.3.5 Marketing and Promotion

iSafety's marketing plan is based on the following factors:

Market analysis:

Continuous market analysis to know the trends and keep the product updated.

Branding and positioning:

Leverage Indra's strong brand identity to reflect the reliability, security and effectiveness of the System.

Trade shows and conferences:

Participate in industry trade shows, conferences and expos to showcase the system and connect with potential customers.

Customer testimonials and case studies:

Compilation of testimonials from satisfied customers who have successfully implemented the system.

Partnerships and alliances:

Use of Indra's network of partners to create joint marketing opportunities.

Customer service and feedback:

Excellence in customer management to support our new sales.

4.3.6 Research Funding and Grants

The exploitation of the iSafety adaptation for VALKYRIES Reference Model may involve the procurement of research funding and grants, National or EU level, to assist in the maturation of the solution, in the refinement of the solution towards the integration of novel concepts and technologies and in the promotion of the solution before communities of practice.

Funding can also be raised through sales opportunities that allow part of the licence fee to be used for product enhancement.

4.3.7 Continuous Research and Development

iSafety is included in Indra's product catalogue list and as such, the Safety Committee analyses monthly innovation opportunities, driving projects and financing opportunities in progress, designing an investment and product roadmap agreed between engineering and the business line.

4.3.8 Regulatory Compliance and Standards

iSafety has the capacity to adapt to the regulations and standards in force in its areas of operation. It currently complies with the following regulations:

- Spanish National Cybersecurity Strategy.
- National Private security law
- Data protection law (LOPD)

Indra develops all its products in compliance with the following norms and standards.

ISO/IEC 12207: This international standard defines processes and activities for the software lifecycle. It provides a framework for the development, operation and maintenance of quality software.

ISO/IEC 27001: Focuses on information security and establishes an information security management system (ISMS). Although not specific to software development, it is relevant to ensuring that data and software systems are secure.

ISO 9001: Although not exclusively focused on software, ISO 9001 establishes quality management standards that apply to the software industry. It may be relevant to quality assurance in software development.

IEEE 829: Defines standards for software test documentation, including test plans, test case specifications and test result reports.

ISO/IEC 25010: Focuses on software product quality, defining quality characteristics and metrics for assessing them. These characteristics include functionality, usability, performance, security and others.

Capability Maturity Model Integration (CMMI): Provides a process improvement framework for software development and maintenance. It is designed to help organizations improve their processes and deliver consistently high-quality software.

Scrum: A widely used agile framework for software development. It is not a standard but provides a structure for managing software projects and is based on agile principles such as collaboration, adaptation and continuous delivery.

ITIL (Information Technology Infrastructure Library): Although focused on IT service management, ITIL includes practices and recommendations for software asset management and change management in the IT environment.

OWASP (Open Web Application Security Project): Although not a standard, OWASP provides a list of the 10 most critical security risks in web applications and offers guidelines and tools to mitigate these risks in software development.

4.3.9 Continuous Research and Development

iSafety's continuous research and development plan is based on the following points:

Needs assessment:

Analysis of market trends, possible adjustments to new regulations, adaptations to new technologies and feedback from end users.

Product roadmap:

Develop and maintain a dynamic product roadmap outlining planned R&D initiatives for the next 1 to 3 years.

Prioritize roadmap elements based on user requirements and market demand.

User-centred design:

Focus the design on the user experience of the system's users.

Integration and interoperability:

Provide the system with the ability to integrate with other emergency management tools, databases, and communication platforms.

Application of AI technology:

Apply AI tools to the system, for continuous learning, scenario simulation, predictive....

Budget and resource allocation:

Indra, as a leading company in technology, allocates part of its budget to research and development to anticipate the needs of the market.

4.3.10 Measures and Evaluation of the Exploitation Plan

To measure and evaluate the effectiveness of the iSafety exploitation plan described in this document we use the following KPIs:

Customer satisfaction: Measured through letters of good execution completed by end clients and feedback reported by users through satisfaction surveys.

Market share and competitive analysis: Analysis of the market share of the system in comparison with competitors.

Return on investment (ROI): Calculation of the financial ROI of the system by comparing the benefits

Practical cases and success stories: Compilation of case studies and success stories and comparison with failures.

4.4. BC4 TASSICA 3 Triage Card

4.4.1 Patent and Intellectual Property Protection

Protecting intellectual property, for TASSICA 3 triage cards, is necessary to safeguard its innovation.

Throughout the Valkyries project, a study of the previous state of the art has been carried out, which has determined, in the case of TASSICA 3, the unique characteristics that make the triage card innovative and useful.

To protect the TASSICA 3 card the following will be used:

1. Patent protection:

- Utility patent: A utility patent protects the functional aspects of an invention.

2. Non-Disclosure Agreements (NDAs):

- In relationships with potential partners, investors or employees, the signing of confidentiality agreements will be requested to protect the confidentiality of their intellectual property.

3. Copyright protection:

- As the TASSICA 3 card includes creative or written content, copyright protection will be applied to prevent unauthorized copying.

4. Trademark Protection:

- Both the TASSICA brand and its distinctive logo are associated with the TASSICA 3 card and are registered.

5. Licenses and Agreements:

- License agreements will always be established that describe the terms, conditions and limitations of use.

4.4.2 Collaboration and Knowledge Transfer

Collaboration and knowledge transfer are vital to the successful development, adoption and scale-up of innovations like TASSICA 3.

Successful collaboration and knowledge transfer are continuous processes that require effective communication, trust, and commitment to shared goals.

Although it is true that throughout the project tasks inherent to this transfer of knowledge have already been carried out, the steps detailed below can be repeated:

- Identify possible collaborators: Search for individuals, organizations or institutions that could benefit from or contribute to the development and implementation of TASSICA 3. This could include healthcare providers, emergency personnel, government agencies and technology partners.
- Establish confidentiality agreements (NDA): When participating in discussions or negotiations with potential collaborators, always ensure that confidential information about TASSICA 3 is protected through NDA to maintain confidentiality.
- Training and Workshops: Training sessions and workshops will be organized to educate employees on how to use TASSICA 3 effectively. Provide practical experience to promote better understanding.
- Data sharing agreements: Data sharing agreements will be established that describe how data will be collected, stored and shared among collaborators while respecting privacy and legal requirements.
- Intellectual Property Rights: As indicated in the previous section, it will be clearly established who the owners of the intellectual property are, respecting them at all times.
- Scaling and adoption plans: As the goal is to scale TASSICA 3 beyond its initial partners, a strategy for its adoption will be developed. It will involve working with regulatory bodies, healthcare institutions or other stakeholders to ensure widespread use.
- Sustainability and Continuity: Planning for the long-term sustainability of TASSICA 3 involves a consideration of maintaining, updating and supporting the relationship over time. To this end, various events related to this task will be scheduled, such as: workshops, conferences, meetings...

- Legal and regulatory compliance: All collaboration and knowledge transfer efforts will comply with relevant laws and regulations, especially in the technology and healthcare sectors.

4.4.3 Industry Engagement and Commercialization

Conducting market research and engaging with the industry is essential to understanding demand for TASSICA 3, determining appropriate pricing models, and identifying potential barriers to adoption.

These are the tasks to perform:

1. Market research:

- a. Identify target markets: In the previous section we have determined both the main markets and sectors where TASSICA 3 can add value as well as potential clients. As a summary, quote again: First Responders and Rescue Teams. Emergency Medical Teams. Healthcare Institutions. Emergency Management Authorities. Government Agencies. NGOs.
- b. Customer segmentation: We will segment potential customers based on certain characteristics, especially their type and geographic location. This will help to adapt our marketing and pricing strategies.
- c. Competitive analysis: Throughout the Valkyries project, possible competitors of the TASSICA 3 card have been analysed and the gaps that it can fill have been identified. These gaps have been cited in the section: Positioning / Competitors 6.1.4.6
- d. Trends and regulations: Throughout the Valkyries project, all regulatory standards in the areas involved have been studied and incorporated into the project. Of course, regulations are a living and dynamic thing that must always be revised in accordance with the markets in which they are applied.
- e. Market size and growth: Section 6.1.4.5. Market targeted and its size explains the size and foreseeable evolution of the market to be considered.

2. Relationship with industry stakeholders:

- a. Networking: Attendance at industry conferences, trade fairs and events related to healthcare, emergency response and disaster management will be necessary. Example: ISAF, SEMES, NCS Security... Make contacts with professionals and potential partners.
- b. Surveys and interviews: Throughout the Valkyries project, surveys and interviews have been conducted with key stakeholders such as health professionals, emergency responders and decision makers to gather information on their needs and weaknesses. It is important that this work continues.
- c. Advisory boards: Advisory boards composed of experts and practitioners from relevant sectors are held to provide valuable insights and guidance.

3. Pricing models:

These are already referred to in section 3.4.6 Positioning (value proposition/competitors/value to outcompete/protection from competitors), but will usually always be done:

- a. Cost analysis: The production and operating costs associated with TASSICA 3 are calculated. This includes production, distribution, maintenance and ongoing support.

- b. Value-based pricing: Determine the value that TASSICA 3 brings to the customer. Price the product based on this perceived value rather than on cost alone.
- c. Competitive pricing: The pricing strategies of its competitors will be analyzed and TASSICA 3 will be positioned competitively.

4. **Overcoming barriers to adoption:**

- a. Education and training: Developing comprehensive training materials and programmes to educate potential users on the effective use of TASSICA 3.
- b. Regulatory compliance: Ensure that TASSICA 3 complies with industry regulations and standards. Address any regulatory hurdles to gain the confidence of potential users.
- c. Data security and privacy: Address data security and privacy concerns.
- d. Integration of user feedback: Continuously gather user feedback and adapt TASSICA 3 based on their input to improve adoption rates.

5. **Marketing strategy:**

- a. Marketing and distribution: A marketing plan will be developed to promote TASSICA 3. This will include online marketing, sales teams and partnerships with distributors.
- b. Distribution channels: Determine the most effective distribution channels to reach target customers.
- c. Launch plan: A comprehensive launch plan will be created, including a timeline, marketing materials and sales strategies.

6. **Continuous improvement**

Continually monitor market trends, customer feedback and adoption rates. Be prepared to iterate and improve TASSICA 3 according to changing market dynamics and customer needs.

4.4.4 **Product Development and Optimization**

Product development and optimization is an ongoing process that requires a deep understanding of user needs and continuous improvement based on feedback and research results. It should be noted that these tasks were carried out during the Valkyries project.

1. **Collect user feedback:**

- a) Surveys and questionnaires: Surveys or questionnaires will continue to be carried out to collect feedback from TASSICA 3 users about their experiences, weaknesses and suggestions for improvement.
- b) User interviews Individual or group interviews will continue to be conducted with users to gain an in-depth understanding of their experiences and the specific challenges they face.
- c) User analysis: User analysis tools will be used to track user behaviour within TASSICA 3. Data will be analysed to identify patterns and areas where users may encounter difficulties.
- d) Support requests and tickets: Review user support requests and tickets to identify recurring issues or feature requests.

2. **Analyse the results of the research:**

- a) Segment user comments: Categorise user feedback into themes or pain points. Identify common issues and opportunities for improvement.

- b) Prioritise feedback: Rank user comments based on factors such as frequency of mention, severity of problem, and alignment with product vision and goals.
- c) Competitive analysis: Comparing TASSICA 3 with similar products on the market by identifying features or functionalities offered by competitors and considering their relevance.

3. **Prioritise feature development:**

User value and impact: Prioritize features that offer the most value to users and have a significant impact on solving their pain points.

- a) Feasibility: Assess the technical feasibility of implementing each feature. Consider resources, time and technical constraints.
- b) Strategic Alignment: Ensure that the selected features fit with the overall product strategy and objectives.
- c) MVP approach: Consider implementing features in a phased approach, starting with a minimum viable product (MVP) and iteratively adding enhancements based on user feedback.
- d) Cost-benefit analysis: Evaluate the costs associated with developing and maintaining each feature against the expected benefits, such as increased user engagement or market competitiveness.

4. **Development and Testing**

- a) Development Roadmap: Create a development roadmap that outlines the schedule and milestones for each enhancement.
- b) User Testing: Involve users in testing and validating new features. Gather feedback during beta testing and iterate based on user response.

5. **Iterate and measure:**

Iterative improvement: Continually iterate features based on real-world usage and feedback. Release regular updates to address issues and make improvements.

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs): Define and track KPIs to measure the success of feature enhancements.

4.4.5 Marketing and Promotion

Marketing and promotion are crucial for raising awareness and boosting uptake of TASSICA 3, especially after a major project like Valkyries.

1. **Understand the target audience:**

Start by identifying the specific audience segments that will benefit most from TASSICA 3. This is covered in sections 3.4.4 Main Identified Customer and 3.4.5 Market aimed and size.

2. **Develop a clear value proposition:**

Develop a compelling and concise value proposition that communicates the unique benefits of TASSICA 3. See 3.4.3 Main Innovation Content.

3. **Create marketing materials:**

Develop a range of marketing materials, including brochures, flyers, infographics and product literature. These materials should be visually appealing and clearly convey the value of TASSICA 3.

4. **Build an online presence:**

Create a professional website dedicated to TASSICA 3. Include detailed product information, features, case studies and user testimonials.

Create a blog where you publish articles that provide valuable information related to triage, emergency response and healthcare.

5. **Use social media:**

Create and maintain active social media profiles on platforms that are relevant to the target audience (e.g. LinkedIn, Twitter and Facebook). Share updates, industry news and interact with audiences.

Use social media advertising to reach a wider audience and promote key messages about TASSICA 3.

6. **Content marketing:**

Develop a content marketing strategy that includes regular blog posts, white papers, e-books and videos. Content should address common industry challenges and show how TASSICA 3 can provide solutions.

7. **Email Marketing:**

Build an email list of potential customers and interested users. Send newsletters, product updates and educational content to keep them informed and engaged.

8. **Take advantage of industry events:**

Attend and participate in industry conferences, trade shows and exhibitions. Showcase TASSICA 3 at these events and use them as networking opportunities with potential customers and partners. Example: ISAF, SEMES, NCS Security...

9. **Public Relations (PR):**

Collaboration with PR professionals to generate media coverage and press releases on TASSICA 3; sharing success stories, case studies and updates with relevant industry publications.

10. **User testimonials and case studies:**

Collect and showcase user testimonials and case studies that highlight the positive impact of TASSICA 3 in real-life situations. Authentic success stories can build trust and credibility.

11. **Partnerships and alliances:**

Explore partnerships with organizations that can help distribute or integrate TASSICA 3 into their solutions.

12. **Webinars and workshops:**

Organize webinars and workshops to provide in-depth knowledge on TASSICA 3 and offer training to potential users. These events can also serve as lead generation opportunities.

13. Offer free trials or demonstrations:

Allow potential customers to try TASSICA 3 through free trials or demonstrations. This hands-on experience can help them understand its value.

14. Monitor and measure:

Use analytics tools to track the effectiveness of marketing efforts. Monitor website traffic, conversion rates, social media engagement and email campaign metrics. Adjust strategies based on data.

15. Feedback and iteration:

Continuously collect feedback from users and potential customers. Use this feedback to refine marketing messages and product positioning.

4.4.6 Regulatory Compliance and Standards

Without mentioning those cross-cutting standards that are not directly related to the design, production and use of triage cards, there are some references that will be considered, such as the following:

- ISO 22320: Emergency management – Requirements for incident response.
- ISO 22396: Societal security – Community resilience – Guidelines for information exchange between organizations.
- EN 15223-1: Medical devices. Symbols to be used with medical device labels, labelling, and information to be supplied.

4.4.7 Research Funding and Grants

Securing research funding and grants for TASSICA 3 is essential for its further development, testing and implementation.

A continuous search for new funding opportunities and grants must be maintained, as these may change over time.

1. Sources of funding:

We will divide them into our own resources and external resources. Own resources basically consist of capital reserves and loans to the company.

External resources may include government agencies, private foundations, corporate grants and research institutions.

Depending on the nature of the institution's capital, we will consider:

1. Government grants

- There are government grant programmes that support healthcare innovation, emergency response technologies or medical device development.

2. Private grants

- Private foundations: Some private foundations provide grants for health research and innovation. Research foundations, medical charities and philanthropic organizations may offer funding opportunities.

- Corporate grants: Some corporations and technology companies have grant programmes that support innovative projects in health and related fields.
- Academic and research institutions: It is possible to partner with universities, academic institutions and research centres that have their own research funding programmes. Collaboration can open doors to additional resources.

4.4.8 Continuous Research and Development

Ongoing research and development (R&D) of a specific product such as the TASSICA 3 Triage Card involves a tailor-made approach to improve the functionality, effectiveness and relevance of the card in its specific context.

Here are some areas of focus for the ongoing R&D of the TASSICA 3 Triage Card

- 1) Improving the triage algorithm: continuously refining and updating the triage algorithm embedded in the card to improve its accuracy and effectiveness in prioritizing patients based on the severity of their condition.
- 2) Data integration: Integrate the triage card with electronic health record (EHR) systems and other medical databases to quickly access patient history and relevant medical information. This integration can enhance the ability of the card to make informed triage decisions.
- 3) Develop and update training materials and protocols for healthcare professionals using the TASSICA 3 Triage Card to ensure that users are proficient in its use.
- 4) User feedback: Establish a feedback mechanism for healthcare professionals to report on the performance of the card in real-life situations. Use this feedback to make iterative improvements.
- 5) Emergency response coordination: Work on integration with emergency response systems to facilitate seamless communication between triage card users and emergency response teams.
- 6) Accessibility and language support: Ensure that the card is accessible to a wide range of users, including those with disabilities, and that it supports multiple languages to cater for different healthcare settings and regions.
- 7) Durability and portability: Continually improve the physical design of the card to make it more durable, portable and easy to use in a variety of emergency settings.
- 8) Regulatory compliance and updates: Staying abreast of healthcare regulations and standards to ensure the TASSICA 3 Triage Card meets the latest requirements and guidelines.
- 9) Cost optimization: Explore ways to reduce the production costs of the triage card without compromising quality and functionality.
- 10) Simulation and testing: Conduct simulated triage scenarios and rigorous testing to evaluate the performance of the card and identify any weaknesses or areas for improvement.
- 11) Environmental impact: Consider the environmental impact of the production and disposal of the card, aiming to minimize waste and use sustainable materials and practices.
- 12) User education and outreach: Provide ongoing education and outreach programmes to healthcare facilities and professionals to promote the effective use of the TASSICA 3 Triage Card.
- 13) Market research: Continuously monitor the evolving needs of healthcare professionals and emergency responders to adapt the card's features to changing requirements.

- 14) Collaboration with healthcare organizations, emergency response agencies and medical researchers to gather information and leverage external expertise for R&D efforts.

Continued R&D of the TASSICA 3 Triage Card is essential to ensure that it remains a valuable tool for healthcare professionals in emergency situations, ultimately improving patient outcomes and streamlining the triage process.

4.4.9 Collaboration with NGOs and Sustainability Initiatives

Working with non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and participating in sustainability initiatives can have a number of benefits for the use of the TASSICA 3 triage card:

1. NGOs often have access to funding, expertise and resources that can support the development, production and distribution of the triage card. Partnerships can help secure the necessary funding and infrastructure.
2. Field testing: NGOs involved in health and emergency response can facilitate field testing of the TASSICA 3 triage card in real-life situations. This will provide valuable information to improve the functionality and usability of the card.
3. NGOs working in different regions have local knowledge and networks. Working with them can help adapt the triage card to specific health contexts and cultural sensitivities, making it more effective in different settings.
4. NGOs often have established distribution channels and partnerships with health facilities in underserved areas. Using these networks can ensure that the triage card reaches the areas where it is most needed.
5. Training and capacity building: NGOs can provide training and capacity building programmes for health professionals and emergency responders on the proper use of the TASSICA 3 triage card, ensuring its effective implementation.
6. Sustainability initiatives: Collaboration with sustainability-focused NGOs can help reduce the environmental impact of triage card production and distribution. This may include the use of sustainable materials, waste reduction or the implementation of recycling programmes.
7. Global reach: NGOs often work on a global scale, allowing the triage card to be introduced in a variety of regions with different health infrastructures. This broadens the potential user base and the impact of the card.
8. Community engagement: NGOs often work with local communities and can help facilitate community acceptance and understanding of the triage card, which can be particularly important in culturally diverse or underserved areas.
9. NGOs can advocate at a political level for the adoption of the TASSICA 3 triage card and ensure that it becomes an integral part of emergency health care systems.
10. Data collection and research: Collaboration with NGOs can facilitate data collection and research initiatives related to the impact of the triage card on health outcomes, helping to continuously improve its effectiveness.
11. Crisis response: In times of natural disasters or public health crises, NGOs can work with emergency response teams, using the triage card to effectively prioritise patient care.
12. Diversify funding: Partnering with sustainability-focused NGOs can open up grant and funding opportunities specifically targeted at projects that align with environmental and social sustainability goals.

4.4.10 Measurement and Evaluation of Exploitation Plan

Measurement and evaluation of the TASSICA 3 triage card operation plan are crucial to assess the effectiveness of the plan and its suitability for the project's objectives. The steps and considerations for measuring and evaluating the operational plan are outlined below:

1. Define clear objectives: First, the objectives and goals of the exploitation plan must be clearly defined. These objectives should be **specific, measurable, achievable, relevant and time-bound (SMART)**.
2. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs): Identify and establish KPIs that are in line with the objectives of the plan. KPIs should be quantifiable metrics that can be used to measure progress and success. Examples of KPIs for the operational plan might include the number of triage cards deployed, user ratings, adoption rates and cost-effectiveness metrics.
3. Data collection: Collect data related to the implementation and outcomes of the plan. This data can come from a variety of sources, such as surveys, user feedback, sales records and operational reports. Data collection methods need to be systematic and consistent.
4. Set specific timelines and milestones for implementation and evaluation of the plan. Periodically review progress against these deadlines to check whether the plan is on schedule.
5. User feedback and surveys: Solicit feedback from users, health professionals and other stakeholders who interact with the TASSICA 3 triage card. Collect qualitative and quantitative feedback on its usability, effectiveness and impact on patient care.
6. Cost-benefit analysis: Assess the cost-effectiveness of the scheme. Compare the costs incurred in implementing the operational plan with the benefits it has generated, such as improved healthcare outcomes, cost savings or increased market share.
7. Measure the adoption rate of the TASSICA 3 triage card in the target regions. Evaluate how often and how effectively it is used in real-life situations.
8. Stakeholder satisfaction: Assess the satisfaction levels of key stakeholders involved in the operational plan, including health professionals, emergency personnel and administrators. A high level of satisfaction is an indication of successful implementation.
9. Ensure that the triage card and its operational plan comply with relevant regulations and quality standards. This includes assessing whether the card complies with health sector standards and patient safety requirements.
10. Market penetration: Measure the penetration and market share of the card in the healthcare sector. Analyse how it competes with similar products or solutions in the market.
11. Continuous improvement: Use the results of the evaluation to identify areas for improvement. If certain aspects of the operational plan are not meeting their objectives, consider making adjustments or improvements to the plan.
12. Reporting and communication: Report regularly on the progress and results of the operational plan to stakeholders, including project sponsors, investors and team members. Transparent communication is essential for accountability and decision-making.
13. Risk assessment: Continually assess and manage risks associated with the exploitation plan. Identify potential obstacles or challenges that may hinder the success of the plan and develop mitigation strategies.

14. Documentation: Maintain detailed records of the implementation of the plan, including budgets, timelines and results.
15. Establish a feedback loop to collect insights and lessons learned from the evaluation process.

Overall, measurement and evaluation of the operational plan should provide valuable information on its effectiveness and help guide decision-making to optimise the impact of the TASSICA 3 triage card on healthcare delivery and patient care.

4.5. BC5 Global COP

4.5.1 Patent and Intellectual Property Protection

The Intellectual Property of the Global COP is solely and exclusively owned by PARTICLE.

PARTICLE protects its IP rights via Copyright Protection, Non-Disclosure Agreements (NDAs) and Licensing Agreements.

4.5.2 Collaboration and Knowledge transfer Identified Customer

The exploitation of the Global COP contemplates the collaboration and knowledge transfer with customers and relevant stakeholders in the public safety and security market. These activities are key to dynamically ensure the continuous improvement of the Global COP, and several initiatives may be explored:

- Complementary partnership agreements to grow the stakeholder ecosystem.
- Commercial presentations and participation in promotional industry and end-users' events.
- Integration with legacy systems owned by prospective customers.
- Training and consultancy services.
- IP agreements for R&D activities.
- Simulation tools (oriented to train and to adapt procedures to extract maximum benefit from the Global COP).

4.5.3 Industry engagement and Commercialization

The exploitation of the Global COP includes the definition of an industry engagement and commercialization plan for the Global COP, incorporating the following activities:

- Conduct technical demonstrations of the Global COP to potential industry partners.
- Engage in collaborative research and innovation projects promoting the Global COP to potential industry partners and prospective customers.
- Perform training sessions targeted to prospective customers.
- Create a network of first adopters to operate as main advocates of the solution.
- Establish a 2-year marketing campaign, including promotional offers, towards prospective customers.
- Create a licensing policy for the Global COP.

4.5.4 Product Development and Optimization

PARTICLE will continue to work on the robustness and maturation of the existing features of the Global COP to attain TRL9. Further, PARTICLE will undertake the development and integration of added-value functions into the Global COP, based on new technological trends and innovations and on the identification of requests elicited by prospective customers.

4.5.5 Marketing and Promotion

The exploitation of the Global COP includes the development of a marketing and promotion plan for the Global COP, encompassing the following elements:

- Market analysis, involving SWOT, PESTEL and Bowman's Strategic Clock tools and detailed competitive analyses, for the definition of market positioning.
- Business model.
- Marketing and promotional campaign (events, social media);
- Networking and partnerships (First adopters initiative);
- Customer experience unit.

4.5.6 Regulatory Compliance and Standards

The Global COP will accommodate the capability to observe the applicable quality and security standards, as well as to comply with the relevant regulatory framework in EU and the specific national legislation of prospective customers. Some reference standards and regulation applicable are the following:

- **NENA/EIDO:** Standard for Emergency Incident Data Object
- **ISO 22320:** Emergency management – Requirements for incident response.
- **ISO 9001:** Establishes quality management standards that apply to the software industry, and support process quality to customers and support.
- **GDPR:** General Data Protection Regulation

4.5.7 Research Funding and Grants

The exploitation of the Global COP may involve the procurement of research funding and grants (National and EU) to assist in the maturation of the solution, in the refinement of the solution towards the integration of novel concepts and technologies and in the promotion of the solution before communities of practice.

4.5.8 Continuous Research and Development

PARTICLE adopts a policy towards the improvement of the products, solutions and services that are part of the company's portfolio. In this context, PARTICLE maintains an innovation watch activity, attentive to the identification and selection of novel concepts, methodologies, technologies and processes capable of contributing to that improvement. Subsequently, a continuous product improvement roadmap plan analyses which novelties are prioritized by the customers and determines the path towards their adoption and integration in specific products, solutions and/or services.

4.5.9 Collaboration with NGOs and Sustainability Initiatives

The exploitation of the Global COP identifies NGOs as part of the targeted customers list. As a result, collaboration with NGOs will be sought as part of the commercialization plan.

4.5.10 Measures and Evaluation of the Exploitation Plan

PARTICLE will assess the execution of the defined exploitation plan for the Global COP, considering the activities and elements identified as part of the marketing and business plan:

- Number of exploitation activities performed.
- Number of short- to mid-term business opportunities identified.
- Volume of sales.
- Return on Investment.
- Number and content of testimonials, feedback and appraisals from customers.

5. Consultation Results for EAB

At the Exploitation workshop held on 19th September, the most relevant opportunities were presented to the EAB, and a consultation process was carried out to evaluate the feedback from the EAB.

The results are shown below

- What is your level of acceptance of the identified opportunity: BC1. SIGRUN as an interoperability framework → 8
- What is your level of acceptance of the identified opportunity: BC2. Reference Implementation of SIGRUN → 7,33
- What is your level of acceptance of the identified opportunity: BC3. ISafety as a Command-and-Control Tool → 7,67
- What is your level of acceptance of the identified opportunity: BC4? Triage Card → 8
- What is your level of acceptance of the identified opportunity: BC5. Valkyries GLOBAL COP → 8,33
- Standardization. How would you rate the quality level of the proposed recommendations, tactics and guidelines? → 7,67
- Certification. What is your level of acceptance of the identified opportunities for the certification? → 7,67
- What is your level of acceptance of new/enhanced conformity assessment criteria for the certification → 7,67

What is your final evaluation of the Valkyries H2020 project? → 8,67

Final comment: *The technological tools that were developed in the framework of the project (especially SIGRUN) are very interesting though standardization has not been achieved.*

A new project *that will serve as the continuation of VALKYRIES seems to be a challenging opportunity.*

The consultation was answered by three members of the EAB and we can see that the most highly valued opportunities are the GLOBAL COP and the SIGRUN reference model, but in general all the opportunities have been very well received and that in general the results of the project are valued positively and it is necessary to continue advancing in the standardisation process and to look for opportunities to continue advancing in the project.

6. Conclusions

All products have been tested for most of the UC and this is a great commercial reference for each of the tools. Each UC had its own execution scenario and operation and both SIGRUN and the other tools have been able to adjust to adapt to the model successfully. We can conclude that the model resulting from this project is easy to implement and that current tools can easily adopt the model.

In terms of procedures, the use of TASSICA 3 triage cards has also been a great achievement and the response from the first responders has been very positive, being able to use the same system in each country. The digitalisation tool of the triage process has a lot of potential and ostensibly improves processing times by avoiding voice communication.

In the more specific case of iSafety as a Command-and-Control tool, the interoperability of the tool has been greatly improved and its integration with simulation technologies allows for the addition of very innovative functionalities. However, it has been seen in the demonstrators that the implementation of these tools is still costly for the agencies and needs to be further improved. Current applications have virtually no integrated systems and integrations are usually very costly. With small changes, very good results can be achieved, as the results of the project show. In the demonstrators themselves, we found that many agencies had no command-and-control applications or that command and control applications had very limited integration capabilities, thus confirming that there is much room for improvement for command-and-control applications.

In terms of the operating model, the customer segments are very similar, which makes a common marketing strategy easy. Providing consultancy services and adjusting the systems according to the budget of each client will be a key factor in the final exploitation of these systems.

It is clear that it is necessary to take a further step in terms of standardisation and in addition to the dissemination of results that will be done at the consortium level and at the level of each partner, one of the proposals is to promote the creation of a standardisation framework of the Valkyries reference model in order to show it as a successful case of implementation of the different UC. It is in fact a very large reference in cross border multi-victim incidents, but it can also be used between agencies in the same country as we have seen.

In the same direction, the EAB's assessments in the consultation process are very positive about the framework and the Global COP and the rest of the Business Cases, and they also see the need to continue advancing in the standardisation process and in the continuity of the project.

7. Annex A – References and bibliography

7.1. Internal references

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7.2. External references

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8. Annex B – Glossary

Acronym	Description
BC	Business Case
COP	Command Operational Picture
MCI	Multi Casualty Incident
UC	Use Case
HTL	Hybrid Twin Labs (Indra's product)

Table 3 – Glossary